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Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 2.4

Authentication and authorisation infrastructure

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1 Publishable summary

Authorisation and authentication processes are a key component of any modern informatics system. Nowadays most online systems require personalisation or restriction of the output data depending on the user identity or permissions. This deliverable tackles the problem of authorising and authenticating users inside of the FNS-Cloud research cloud.

The deliverable starts with the introduction to the topic and explanation on why the most common approach of shipping local authorisation and authentication (AAI) solution is not suitable for research clouds. Then, a solution is proposed – integration of an AAI into the FNS-Cloud. While AAI can have many meanings and definitions, in this case it's a central user identity provider, from which application providers can obtain FNS-Cloud members identities. Additionally, the possibility of connecting to other research clouds via federation is discussed, although that is an ongoing effort.

After proposing the solution, then research is carried out to find and compare software that can be utilised in creating such an infrastructure. It is worth noting that in order to reduce maintenance costs only software which is open-source and free to use was considered in this deliverable. After the evaluation and discussion between FNS-Cloud project technical beneficiaries an open-source identity and access management solution Keycloak was selected and implemented as the base of the proposed AAI system. Additionally, this deliverable provides a manual for application developers on how to integrate with the FNS Cloud AAI.

2 Introduction

While a big chunk of scientific services and research artifacts is openly accessible to any interested party, there are several reasons why resource or service owners may want to restrict access to their resources to certain users or groups, or profile the returned data based on which user tries to access it. In those cases, authentication and authorisation mechanisms come into play. Those two terms are commonly used together but they have distinct meanings.

Figure 2.1 Description of authentication

Authentication (figure 2.1) is an act of validating that the users are indeed who they claim to be, using one or more authentication factors. In web systems the most commonly used authentication factor is a combination of username (or email) and password credentials. That being said now-a-days many systems containing data that requires security often offer (or even enforce) multi-factor authentication, meaning that the user needs to pass several authentication factors in order to prove his identity. Additional factors range from sms/email received or mobile app generated codes to biometric data depending on the systems security requirements.

Figure 2.2 Description of authorisation

On the other hand, authorisation (figure 2.2), often also named “access control”, is a process of granting (or denying) access to a specific resource or service. A good example is obtaining access to a protected file on the server or getting access to administrative functions in the application.

In secure web systems both processes work in conjunction and authorisation should always follow authentication for any non-publicly available resource.

2.1 “Standard” approach and its shortcomings

The typical web applications security approach is to ship its own local authentication and authorisation mechanism as a part of the application. This means that the application needs to contain its own user database and if a user wants to access multiple applications, he needs to create an account and login in each of the services.

This proved to be a very suboptimal and problematic solution, when applied to group of related applications, such as the infrastructure developed for FNS-Cloud due to a variety of reasons, including:

- Time consuming process of user registration, with the need to provide same data multiple times (in each application registration form),
- Tedious process of keeping data in sync in all the applications, including organisation affiliation data,
- Tricky privacy management – no centralised place to revoke all the consents if needed,
- Overloading users with the need to manage multiple passwords - which leads to either reusing the same password across multiple databases or the need to use password reminder function often (especially if multiple services have distinct password policies),
- Lot of effort needed to integrate data owned by user in another service, due to lack of standard contract,
- Difficult and non-consistent user and permission management for service administrators,
- Costs of developing and management of own authentication/authorisation mechanism.

2.2 What is an AAI?

The term AAI refers to Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure, which is a middleware system consisting of a set of protocols that allows delegation of user authorisation and authentication processes from one system to another.

It is worth noting that this definition is quite broad and can be used to describe a whole range of different systems. Therefore, in the context of the FNS-Cloud project we define AAI as a central Single Sign-On system that supports identity federation (via federated account linking) and that can be referenced for authentication and authorisation purposes by any other FNS applications.

Single Sign-On is an authentication scheme that allows users to login into multiple independent web applications or systems using the same set of credentials.

Identity federation means that the authentication of a user is no longer limited to one central identity provider, but rather it is possible to authenticate users in any of the connected identity providers. Federated account linking takes this idea a step further and creates a local account for the user instead of just passing through the federated identity. This brings several benefits including better knowledge and management of users using AAI for administrators and ability for users to login via multiple identity brokers while still having the same identity “inside” the cloud.

Therefore, by using AAI a user should be able to verify (login) himself once, for example in his home organisation (university that is connected to AAI) and then he should have access to all of the resources and services connected to the infrastructure, provided he has sufficient access level.

Figure 2.2.1 Difference between «standard» old approach (without AAI) and Single Sign-On (with AAI)

Figure 2.2.1 describes the difference between “standard” old-fashioned approach system, where a user needs to authenticate in every service he is using separately and SSO system, where authenticates once and then can use a variety of connected services (including services provided by other user groups, for example other universities).

2.2.1 Benefits of AAI

Creating Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure solves the issues mentioned in paragraph 2.1:

- User only needs to register once, in his home organisation (or even can be registered by a home organisation administrator) or in the central system,
- User has only one place where he needs to update his data,
- Privacy management is simple since user has one place to manage his consents,
- User needs to remember only one password. Therefore, he can focus on making it more complex and secure,
- Common contract between all the connected services - user ID stays the same between all services, so it’s easy to link his data together,
- Consistent management of user and authorisation data in one central panel,
- User information can also be aligned with data provided by the user’s home organisation to keep data more up to date and provide better user verification (for example universities will verify their employees face-to-face).

2.2.2 AAI-Flow

Figure 2.2.2.1 Simplified AAI flow chart

Figure 2.2.2.1 describes a simplified flow of how authentication and authorisation infrastructure work in modern applications. Authentication claims are pieces of information, for example in a form of token that contain data about currently logged in user. It is worth noting that usually AAI-client applications do not perform any validation of those claims and rely completely on the AAI system to verify their truthfulness. After the claims are verified, applications can obtain and trust the received user details and perform authorisation based on user access rights (for example: application roles or groups the user is a part of). In the presented flow chart, it is solely the application's purpose to perform the authorisation process and AAI is only responsible for management of access rights and providing the correct rights to application. However, it is sometimes feasible to delegate the authorisation process completely to AAI, for example if multiple applications share similar authorisation rules, although this approach is very difficult for 3rd party applications.

Figure 2.2.2.2 AAI Local login / Federated identity flow chart

Figure 2.2.2.2 presents the two distinct login options in the standard AAI system. In the «local» option, users can login via the AAI built-in authentication mechanism (for example: user/password credentials), thus leaving the verification of credentials to AAI. Alternatively, the user can choose any of the connected federated identity providers that are trusted by AAI to verify himself in that system and then get verified in AAI. It is worth noting that when logging in via a federated identity provider used login credentials are not shared with AAI at any point.

2.3 AARC

Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC) initiative was launched in 2015 and is funded by European projects such as the European Union’s Horizon 2020.

The team behind this initiative was responsible for creating AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA) - a set of software building blocks that can be utilised to implement AAI solutions for research collaborations and AARC Guidelines - a set of documents that are targeted at helping communities to implement and operate their own AAI more effectively and in an interoperable way (both in terms of architecture and policies). It is worth noting that BPA aim is not to provide a single generic solution, but rather to provide software architects and other technical decision makers tried and tested components that can be utilised in building their own customised solution that matches their requirements.

Figure 5.1 AARC Blueprint Architecture

The final version of BPA (seen on Figure 5.1) consists of five layers that are grouped by their functional roles:

- User identity – services that provide electronic identities that can be utilised by users participating in the research collaboration,
- Community attribute services – services and components related to managing and providing information about users in form of attributes, groups and roles additional to the information already provided by Idps user identity layer,
- Access protocol translation – defines and administrative, technical and policy boundaries between the internal/external services and resources,
- Authorisation – contains elements to control how users can interact with services and resources,
- End-services – responsible for the interaction between external services and other elements of the AAI.

3 FNS Cloud AAI Specification

While there are multiple open access community AAI's that could be utilised in creation of authentication and authorisation infrastructure, such as: Elixir AAI, B2ACCESS, EGI Check-In or eduTEAMS, the decision was made to instead implement a self-hosted, standalone infrastructure and optionally later allow some of the 3rd party AAI solutions to connect and exchange identities via identity federation. This decision was based on two factors:

- the level of the user accounts and user data management that is required by this project,
- explicit dependencies on infrastructures from outside of the project were deemed undesirable.

3.1 Evaluation of software

The absolute minimal requirements for software used in building AAI were:

- free to use,
- open-source,
- actively maintained,
- self-hosted (no dependencies on external components),
- usage/support of known protocols, such as: OAuth, OIDC, SAML.

Even with those requirements in mind, there is a huge amount of software that can be used in building Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructures. It would be unfeasible to compare every one of them, hence the final list comprises of:

- suggestions from FNS-Cloud project members about software they have encountered or used in past,
- software that is known to power other known European AAI's,
- other well-known software (based on google search engine results).

Therefore, final software evaluation list comprises of:

- CAS,
- Gluu,
- Indigo-IAM,
- Keycloak,
- OpenAM,
- Shibboleth,
- Unity IDM,
- WSO2.

The evaluation will be divided into a few categories where appropriate scores will be assigned. The scores will be relative between projects and will be placed on scale 1-10.

3.1.1 DevOps Maintenance

This criterion focuses on how easy the initial setup is. Things that have been considered:

- installation process on the server,
- quality of documentation,
- official container image availability,
- how many separate components (container images) does the whole system consist of,
- how much configuration is needed to get the system to working state and if it can be done via administration UI or does it need to be done by setting variables or properties files.

Software	No of container images	Installation complexity	Configuration	Score	Notes
CAS	1	Moderate	Some needed, partial UI provided	7	
Gluu	Multiple	Moderate	Moderate amount that needs to be done to link all the different components with each other. Some configuration is done in UI, some needs to be done in files	6	Software is split into several container images with distinct purposes, allowing for better modularisation, but at the same time installation is a bit more complex.
Indigo-IAM	1	Simple	Some is needed, no UI provided	7	
Keycloak	1	Simple	Very little needed to start, most of it can be done via UI	9	
OpenAM	1	Moderate	Some needed, most can be done via UI	7	
Shibboleth	No official container image	Difficult (there is a helper script though)	Moderate amount needed, there is UI but it covers only small part of configuration	3	
Unity IDM	No official container image	Moderate	Some needed, partially can be done via UI	5	
WSO2	Multiple	Simple, but documentation could be better	Some needed, most can be done via UI	8	

3.1.2 Popularity

Comparing software popularity is always a non-trivial task. Since only open-source projects were considered, the popularity was measured by number of github stars (which somewhat reflects community interest in the project) and if present official docker image downloads (from dockerhub, which somewhat reflects the amount of running installations).

Software	Stars	Downloads	Score	Notes
CAS	8.8k	500K+	8	
Gluu	325	1M+	7	
Indigo-IAM	65	10K+	4	
Keycloak	9.6k	100M+	10	

OpenAM	389	100K+	5	
Shibboleth	N/A	100K+	6	Git stars are inadequate, since the project is primarily hosted elsewhere. Also, there is no official image present, therefore the most popular non-official image was taken as reference. Some bonus points added since it is well known in industry.
Unity IDM	15	N/A	3	There is no official docker image and no unofficial image could be found in docker hub either, so rating is based only on github
WSO2	465	500K+	6	

3.1.3 Feature completeness

This criterion focuses on availability of additional features that could be beneficiary to the infrastructure.

Software	2FA/MFA	Identity federation	Built in user management	Score	Notes
CAS	Y	Y	N	7	
Gluu	Y (Casa)	Y	Y	10	Most features, lot of MFA options
Indigo-IAM	N	Y	Y	6	
Keycloak	Y	Y	Y	8	
OpenAM	Y	Y	Y	8	
Shibboleth	Y (paid)	Y	N	4	Identity federation requires some additional work, and 2fa integration in docs assumes a paid service
Unity IDM	Y	Y	Y	8	
WSO2	Y	Y	Y	8	

3.1.4 Support

This criterion will focus on the long-term support that can be expected. Things that will be considered include:

- What is the level of community contribution in the project (since all of the projects are open-source - based on github contributors)?
- What's the profile of the company behind the project - is it a big enterprise, small enterprise or an open-source initiative? How long has the company existed?
- Is there a commercial version of the software?
- Is the software used in other European infrastructures?

Software	Community / contributors	Current company profile	Commercial version	Score	Notes
CAS	~285	Well established non-profit foundation, with over 120 paying member institutions, started 2012	None, but commercial support available via 3 rd parties	8	
Gluu	~50	Small enterprise, established 2009	Gluu Enterprise	6	
Indigo-IAM	5	Italian national institute	None	3	Known to be used in some EU AAls
Keycloak	~500	Open-source but under RedHat (big enterprise) stewardship	RedHat SSO, Aerobase	9	
OpenAM	~60	Open-source community organisation since 2018, previously ForgeRock	ForgeRock IDM? But not sure what the direct connection is	4	
Shibboleth	N/A	Shibboleth consortium, founded 2013. Over 50 paying members, including SWITCH and Internet2	None, but extra support available to consortium members	7	
Unity IDM	18	Open-source with some academic institutions support	None	4	Known to be used in some EU AAls (ex. B2Access)
WSO2	~150	Medium sized enterprise, established 2005	Yes	7	

3.1.5 Additional information

Software	Notes
CAS	
Gluu	Composes several open-source projects underneath, instead of rewriting things, including: Shibboleth SAML IDP, OpenDJ or Kong
Indigo-IAM	Version 2 is supposed to be based on Keycloak ¹
Keycloak	Has been used in the past by some of the FNS-Cloud project members.
OpenAM	
Shibboleth	
Unity IDM	
WSO2	Unclear situation regarding updates in open-source version ²

3.2 Selected technology

After considering evaluation done in paragraph 3.1 the decision was made to develop the FNS-Cloud project AAI using Keycloak. The decision was based on factors such as:

- open-source community size regarding the project,
- several commercial projects based on it,
- trust in it placed by Indigo-IAM (which is working on next version of their IAM, based on Keycloak),
- support for all the features we require at the moment,
- relatively easy setup and maintenance,
- FNS-Cloud beneficiaries recommendations / usage experience.

¹<https://indico.cern.ch/event/834658/contributions/3564700/attachments/1907306/3150242/IAM-FIM4R-Fermilab-12092019.pdf>

² <https://wso2.com/identity-and-access-management/install/download/?type=docker>

4 Manual for integration with the FNS Cloud AAI

Since the decision was made to utilise Keycloak as the core of FNS-Cloud AAI, connecting and securing an application that wants to be a part of FNS-Cloud is simple.

To connect an application to FNS-Cloud AAI developer can use one of two protocols:

- SAML
- OIDC

The difference between them is not that important in the context of this document, although for new applications that do not have SAML dependencies already implemented, OIDC is probably a better and recommended choice, as it was made with modern applications (“rich” webapps, mobile apps) in mind. OIDC will then be the assumed choice further in this document.

After picking a protocol that the application will use, the developer has to pick a client library (or write one) depending on the language that application is developed with. Keycloak offers custom made client libraries for some of the programming languages (java, javascript), which are the recommended way of connection. In the case that the application is built using another programming language or wants to offer a variety of authorisation methods instead of relying only on FNS-Cloud AAI, a generic OIDC/SAML client library can also be used.

After picking a client library to be used, it needs to be implemented into the project. Please refer to your client library documentation or Keycloak documentation³ for detailed information on how to do that, as it will vary a lot depending on your choice.

At this point contacting FNS-Cloud support is required in order to obtain ClientID and secret key for the application. Following information will need to be provided:

- Application type (“standard” backend generated webapp, SPA, mobile application, ...)
- Short description
- Protocol that will be used (OIDC/SAML)
- Web URLs to which the application will be able to redirect after authentication

Once ClientID and secret key is received, it can be put into client library configuration and the setup process should be finished. Further assistance can be provided on request.

Additionally, there is an ongoing effort to enable OpenID Connect dynamic client registration feature. This feature should simplify and automate to a degree the process of obtaining credentials (ClientID, secret, ...) for the application from the developer perspective, although at the time of writing this deliverable it has not yet been properly tested and therefore cannot be recommended.

³ https://www.keycloak.org/docs/latest/securing_apps/

5 Conclusion

This deliverable covers a very important aspect of FNS Cloud IT architecture – Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure. After evaluation of possible options: utilising an already existing AAI infrastructure provided by another project, or creating a standalone solution, the decision was made to create own independent AAI. Research was conducted to compare technological components used to create such infrastructures and after evaluation one technology was selected and made available for use with all of FNS-Cloud projects. Manual on connecting to the infrastructure was also provided as a part of this deliverable.

The AAI is envisioned as a centralised authentication piece that will contain all the FNS-Cloud members accounts. The participation in AAI will be voluntary, so it will be decided separately for each application or service by the owning party. At the time of writing this deliverable there needs to be some work done on the AAI side in order to connect a new application to the AAI, but, as mentioned in the manual paragraph, further work will be conducted on testing the OpenID Connect dynamic client registration feature to allow FNS-Cloud members to manage connections between AAI and their applications in a more automated and equal way - meaning that each member organisation will be able to connect as many applications as they wish.

Further development of AAI will focus on alignment with AARC project principles and guidelines, that were described in this deliverable. Additionally, there are ongoing efforts focused on the abilities to federate identities between FNS-Cloud AAI and other AAIs, such as eduGAIN and EOSC.

